

Case Report in Dermatology

Skin-Picking Disorder in Prader–Willi Syndrome: A Case Report and Multidisciplinary Management Approach

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Abstract

Skin-picking disorder (SPD), also known as dermatillomania, is a body-focused repetitive behavior characterized by compulsive skin manipulation leading to tissue damage. Although commonly observed in Prader–Willi Syndrome (PWS), it is frequently underrecognized and may be misdiagnosed as a primary dermatological condition.

We report the case of a 25-year-old patient with PWS, morbid obesity, and insulin-treated diabetes mellitus, presenting with multiple chronic painless ulcers progressing over six months. A multidisciplinary therapeutic approach was implemented, including local wound care with a hyaluronic acid-based healing cream, occlusive dressings, and three sessions of injectable platelet-rich fibrin (I-PRF), combined with psychiatric management using N-acetylcysteine.

This combined strategy resulted in complete wound healing within 45 days and a significant reduction in compulsive skin-picking behavior.

This case highlights the importance of early recognition of the behavioral origin of skin lesions in PWS and supports the effectiveness of an integrated multidisciplinary approach combining dermatological and psychiatric interventions.

Keywords: Chronic ulcers; Dermatillomania; N-acetylcysteine; Prader–Willi syndrome; Skin-picking disorder.

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INTRODUCTION

Prader–Willi Syndrome (PWS) is a rare genetic disorder caused by the absence of expression of paternal genes in the chromosomal region 15q11–q13. It is characterized by hypotonia, hyperphagia leading to obesity, intellectual disability, and a distinctive behavioral phenotype.

Among behavioral manifestations, skin-picking disorder (SPD), also referred to as dermatillomania, represents one of the most frequent and clinically challenging conditions. SPD is classified among obsessive–compulsive and related disorders and is characterized by repetitive, compulsive manipulation of the skin, often resulting in significant tissue damage and chronic lesions [1].

In individuals with PWS, skin-picking behavior is particularly prevalent and may be associated with emotional dysregulation, anxiety, and cognitive impairment. Patients often show reduced pain perception and limited awareness of the behavior, which contributes to the persistence and severity of lesions.

Despite its clinical relevance, SPD in PWS is frequently underrecognized or misdiagnosed as a primary dermatological condition, such as chronic ulcers or trophic lesions. This may delay appropriate management and lead to unnecessary or ineffective treatments.

For this reason, early recognition of the behavioral origin of skin lesions is crucial. A multidisciplinary approach, integrating dermatological care with psychiatric and behavioral interventions, is essential for effective management.

This case report aims to highlight the diagnostic challenges and therapeutic strategies in managing SPD in a patient with Prader–Willi Syndrome.

CASE REPORT

We report the case of a 25-year-old patient with Prader–Willi Syndrome (PWS), morbid obesity, and insulin-treated diabetes mellitus, who presented with multiple chronic painless skin ulcers evolving over a period of six months.

According to the patient's caregiver, a daily habit of repetitive skin picking had been observed, suggesting a behavioral origin of the lesions.

Dermatological examination revealed multiple well-defined ulcers measuring between 2 and 4 cm in diameter, characterized by irregular and jagged margins, a hemorrhagic base, and surrounding skin showing areas of atrophy and scarring. Lesions were distributed over the right hemithorax (Figure 1a), right iliac region, upper limbs, gluteal region (Figure 1b), and lower limbs.

Histopathological examination demonstrated dermal edema and fragmented collagen fibers, supporting the diagnosis of SPD.

A multidisciplinary treatment approach was initiated. Local wound management included the application of a hyaluronic acid-based healing cream combined with occlusive dressings. In addition, three sessions of injectable platelet-rich fibrin (I-PRF) were performed to promote tissue regeneration (Figure 1c).

Concomitantly, psychiatric management was introduced, including treatment with N-acetylcysteine at a dose of 1200 mg/day, aimed at reducing compulsive behavior.

The patient showed progressive clinical improvement, with complete wound healing achieved within 45 days. Furthermore, a significant reduction in skin-picking behavior was observed during follow-up.

Figure 1. (a) Ulcer measuring approximately 3 cm in diameter, with irregular margins and perilesional skin showing thickening and atrophy on the right hemithorax. (b) Ulcer with perilesional skin atrophy on the left gluteal region. (c) Right hemithorax lesion after three sessions of injectable platelet-rich fibrin (I-PRF).

Figure 1a

Figure 1b

Figure 1c

DISCUSSION

Prader–Willi Syndrome (PWS) is a rare genetic disorder caused by the absence of expression of paternal genes in the chromosomal region 15q11–q13 and is characterized by hypothalamic–pituitary dysfunction. In adulthood, the clinical phenotype is dominated by hyperphagia leading to severe obesity, cognitive impairment, and a spectrum of behavioral and psychiatric disturbances, including SPD [2].

Skin-picking represents a core component of the behavioral phenotype of PWS, often associated with temper outbursts, compulsive behaviors, insistence on routines, and increased vulnerability to affective and psychotic disorders [3]. Previous studies have shown that patients with PWS frequently engage in skin picking on pre-existing lesions, such as scars or nevi, typically without significant pain perception and with limited awareness of the behavior [4,5]. These features contribute to the persistence and severity of skin damage.

Despite its high prevalence, SPD in PWS is frequently underestimated or misdiagnosed in clinical practice, often being mistaken for primary dermatological conditions [6]. This may lead to inappropriate management and delays in addressing the underlying behavioral component. In our case, the lesions were initially interpreted as trophic or diabetic ulcers, highlighting the importance of considering a behavioral etiology in patients with atypical or non-healing skin lesions.

The pathophysiology of skin-picking behavior in PWS is not fully understood but is likely multifactorial, involving emotional dysregulation, anxiety, and abnormalities in impulse control. Behavioral triggers such as boredom, stress, or frustration have been consistently reported, further supporting the compulsive nature of the disorder [6].

From a therapeutic perspective, our case supports the effectiveness of a multidisciplinary approach. The combination of local wound care, including occlusive dressings and hyaluronic acid-based treatments, with regenerative strategies such as injectable platelet-rich fibrin (I-PRF), contributed to rapid tissue healing. Importantly, the integration of psychiatric management played a key role in controlling the underlying compulsive behavior.

N-acetylcysteine (NAC), administered at 1200 mg/day in our patient, has been reported to reduce repetitive and compulsive behaviors, possibly through modulation of glutamatergic neurotransmission [8]. In our case, NAC was associated with a significant reduction in skin-picking behavior, supporting its potential role as an adjunctive treatment in PWS.

Overall, this case highlights the importance of early recognition of skin-picking disorder in patients with Prader–Willi Syndrome and underscores the need for an integrated, multidisciplinary management strategy addressing both dermatological and psychiatric aspects of the condition.

CONCLUSION

SPD in Prader–Willi Syndrome is a frequent yet often underrecognized condition that may lead to significant cutaneous morbidity. This case highlights the importance of considering a behavioral etiology in patients presenting with atypical or non-healing skin lesions.

Early diagnosis and a multidisciplinary approach integrating dermatological and psychiatric management are essential for effective treatment. Our findings support the potential benefit of combining local wound care with pharmacological and behavioral interventions in improving both skin healing and compulsive behaviors.

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Ethics Approval: Ethical review and approval were not required for this case report in accordance with local regulations.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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